

CULTUROLOGY

МЕТОДЫ ВЫЯВЛЕНИЯ СПОРТИВНЫХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ У ДЕТЕЙ

Рагимов М.

ORCID: 0009-0008-4275-4237,

канд. пед. наук,

Нахчыванский государственный университет,

г. Нахчыван, Азербайджан

Рзаев О.

ORCID: 0009-0007-6377-255X,

Нахчыванский государственный университет,

г. Нахчыван, Азербайджан

METHODS FOR IDENTIFYING CHILDREN'S SPORTS APTITUDE

Rahimov M.

ORCID: 0009-0008-4275-4237

Ph.D., Nakhchivan State University,

Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

Rzayev O.

ORCID: 0009-0007-6377-255X

Nakhchivan State University

Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

Аннотация

Физическое воспитание детей всегда было в центре внимания как азербайджанских, так и мировых ученых. Выдающиеся мыслители, такие как Низами Гянджеви, Мухаммед Физули, Гасан бек Зардаби, Марагали Авхади, Платон, Аристотель, Иоанн Амос Коменский, Жан-Жак Руссо, Петр Лесгафт и другие, структурировали образование и воспитание детей по возрастным группам. По мнению известного интеллектуала Гасан бека Зардаби, физическое воспитание играет решающую роль в успешной реализации интеллектуального и нравственного развития. Для улучшения этих качеств детей исторически делили на возрастные группы. К разделению детей на возрастные группы в ходе образовательного процесса разные учёные подходили по-разному. Выдающийся азербайджанский поэт и философ Марагали Авхади, говоря о физическом воспитании, предложил физические упражнения и игры, соответствующие возрастным периодам детей. Эту идею проведения физического воспитания в соответствии с возрастными особенностями следует рассматривать как значительное достижение для своего времени. В 7-8-летнем возрасте, поскольку кости еще развиваются и приближаются к строению костей взрослого человека, рекомендуются виды спорта, требующие частых прыжков и ловкости, такие как баскетбол, гандбол, прыжки в длину. Это связано с тем, что на этом этапе скелетная система претерпевает значительные изменения, и занятия такими видами деятельности помогают повысить прочность костей и общее физическое развитие. В возрастном периоде 8-12 лет продолжается развитие всех органов и систем у детей и подростков. Окостенение костей и развитие мышц ускоряются, и к 12 годам кости уже не отличаются от костей взрослого человека. На этом этапе в качестве подходящих видов спорта для детей можно рекомендовать виды спорта, требующие ловкости, гибкости, скорости реакции, внимания и психологической выносливости, такие как дзюдо, футбол, настольный теннис, бадминтон. Эти виды спорта помогают развивать физические и умственные способности, необходимые для дальнейшего роста и развития.

Abstract

The physical education of children has always been a focus of attention for both Azerbaijani and global scholars. Prominent thinkers such as Nizami Ganjavi, Mahammad Fuzuli, Hasan bay Zardabi, Maragali Avhadi, Plato, Aristotle, John Amos Comenius, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Peter Lesgaft, and others have structured children's education and upbringing based on age groups. According to the renowned intellectual Hasan bay Zardabi, physical education plays a crucial role in successfully implementing intellectual and moral development. P.F. Lesgaft regarded physical education as one of the primary tools for shaping willpower, character, moral upbringing, intellectual ability, physical activity, and aesthetic appreciation. To improve these qualities, children have historically been divided into age groups. The division of children into age groups during the educational process has been approached differently by various scholars. The prominent Azerbaijani poet and philosopher Maragali Avhadi, when discussing physical education, proposed physical exercises and games suited to children's age periods. This idea of aligning physical education with age-specific characteristics should be regarded as a significant development for its time. At the age of 7-8, as the bones are still developing and approaching the structure of adult bones, sports that require frequent jumping and agility, such as basketball, handball, and long jump, are recommended. This is because during this stage, the skeletal system is undergoing significant changes, and engaging in such

activities helps in promoting bone strength and overall physical development. During the age period of 8-12, the development of all organs and systems in children and adolescents continues. The ossification of bones and the development of muscles accelerate, and by the age of 12, the bones no longer differ from those of an adult. In this stage, sports that require agility, flexibility, reaction time, attention, and psychological endurance, such as judo, soccer, table tennis, and badminton, can be recommended as suitable sports for children. These sports help develop physical and mental skills essential for further growth and development.

Ключевые слова: дети, физическое воспитание, спортсмены, возрастная группа, дети которые начинают.

Keywords: children, physical education, athlete, age group, swimming, acceleration, children who start.

The physical education of children has always been a focus of attention for both Azerbaijani and global scholars. Prominent thinkers such as Nizami Ganjavi, Mahammad Fuzuli, Hasan bay Zardabi, Maragali Avhadi, Plato, Aristotel, John Amos Comenius, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Peter Lesgaft, and others have structured children's education and upbringing based on age groups. According to the renowned intellectual Hasan bay Zardabi, physical education plays a crucial role in successfully implementing intellectual and moral development. P.F. Lesgaft regarded physical education as one of the primary tools for shaping willpower, character, moral upbringing, intellectual ability, physical activity, and aesthetic appreciation. To develop these qualities, children have historically been divided into age groups. The division of children into age groups during the educational process has been approached differently by various scholars. The prominent Azerbaijani poet and philosopher Maragali Avhadi, when discussing physical education, proposed physical exercises and games suited to children's age periods. This idea of aligning physical education with age-specific characteristics should be regarded as a significant development for its time. Plato defined the following age group in nurture. At the age of 3-6 children should be brought up through games on state playgrounds. At the age of 12-16, they should undergo physical training in palestra schools, etc. [1]. So, Plato considered physical training for children to be most suitable primarily between the ages of 12-16. Aristotle divided the period of age into three groups, comprising seven periods: The period from birth to the age of 7. The period from 7 to 14 years old. The period from 14 to 21 years old. Nizami Ganjavi also shared this perspective. He classified children's development into three stages: the first stage from birth to seven years old, the second stage from seven to fourteen years old, and the third stage from fourteen to twenty — one years old. The Czech educator John Amos Comenius defined age groups follows: The period from birth to 6 years old. The period from 6 to 12 years old. The period from 12 to 18 years old. Jean-Jacques Rousseau defined the age groups of children as follows: The period from birth to 2 years old. The period from 2 to 12 years old. The period from 12 to 15 years old. The period from 15 years old to the age of maturity. In modern era, when involving children in various sports activities, the anatomical and physiological changes in their bodies, according to their age group, must be taken into account in a scientifically justified form. So, if we look at the growth of children at different ages, we see that the period from birth to 3 years is considered a period of rapid physical development. 3-6 years old children [77- 84%] behavioral disorders occur. Fatigue occur often [2].

From 6 to 11-12 years old, the development of all organs and systems of children and adolescents continues [3]. The rapid growth period of a child's body occurs from birth to one year and during puberty ages 11-15. In this stage, the height increases by 7-8 cm per year, and sometimes even by 10 cm [3]. The period of completion of sexual maturity of young people depends on their gender and individual characteristics: It occurs in girls at the age of 12-16, in boys at the age of 13-18. At this stage, psychological and physical development mostly ends [2]. However, this age classification has recently been demanded to change. This is because the issue of acceleration has started to manifest itself. Acceleration, derived from the Latin word *acceleratio*, refers to the speeding up of physical and psychological development during childhood [2]. Therefore, when involving children in sports programs, the age group from previous years should be re-evaluated. In the modern era, the development and diversification of sports, along with the significant differences in training methods for these sports, make it crucial to determine at what age a child should begin practicing a particular sport. An athlete's future level of achievement is highly dependent on the sport they choose to pursue in their childhood. Not all children know which sport is suitable for their body. Most of them choose a sport based on their parents' wishes or because their friends or peers are involved in that sport, without considering whether it aligns with their anatomical and physiological structure. Sometimes, children who start a sport this way manage to achieve high results later. However, this often happens by chance. In many cases, a child initially practices a sport by chance, but eventually either switches to a different sport or, after failing to achieve any results, becomes discouraged and completely distances themselves from sports. Many children also fail to understand that achieving high results in sports requires more than just planned and regular training under the guidance of a highly qualified coach. At the same time, the athlete's anatomical and physiological characteristics, as well as their psychological traits, must align with the sport they choose [3]. In many countries around the world, this process is carried out in different ways. For example, in some countries, children focus only on general physical preparation until the age of 15. Afterward, based on certain tests, it is recommended which specific sport the child should pursue. In some countries, children are advised to enroll in a specific sport based on their physical indicators, body measurements, and psychological condition. In such cases, the child's age and enthusiasm for the sport are not taken into account. Long-term observations have led to the conclusion that none of the methods mentioned above fully meet the requirements of the

modern era [4]. Based on our long-term observations, it can be concluded that it is advisable to scientifically organize the process of selecting a sport for children. A child's height, weight, agility, gender, age, and many other characteristics should serve as measurement units to determine which sport is most suitable for them. Proper guidance is essential for achieving great success in their future lives.

While doing so, it is crucial to take the child's desires into account and provide them with the right direction. Numerous observations of children have led to the conclusion that children aged 2-3 can perform activities such as running, catching, jumping, playing water games in shallow areas under the supervision of a teacher, and simple acrobatic movements. During this age period, children can quickly master swimming movements and various acrobatic exercises in line with their developmental level. [5]. Taking into account the above, it may be more beneficial to use the step-by-step principle in choosing a sport for children. Children should be selected not once, but several times in stages, and directed to sports training according to the above parameters. [6]. At the age of 4-5, children can engage in swimming, dynamic games, gymnastics, running over various distances, and jumping. In addition to these activities, considering their weight, anthropometric measurements, physiological development, psychological state, and enthusiasm, they can also be involved in sports requiring agility and flexibility, such as swimming, acrobatics, artistic gymnastics, and others. Children at this age who practice swimming can learn it quickly because their long bones are hollow, making their body density lower, and they expend less energy to stay afloat. Young children can achieve high results in swimming more quickly. In sports like artistic gymnastics and acrobatics, younger children tend to perform better because their joints are more flexible than those of adults. While children should focus on one of these sports, they should also continue practicing other sports for general physical preparation. It is possible that in the later stages of their development, they may find that they are more suited to a different sport [7]. At the age of 7-8, as the bones are still developing and approaching the structure of adult bones, sports that require frequent jumping and agility, such as basketball, handball, and long jump, are recommended. This is because during this stage, the skeletal system is undergoing significant changes, and engaging in such activities helps in promoting bone strength and overall physical development. During the age period of 8-12, the development of all organs and systems in children and adolescents continues. The ossification of bones and the development of muscles accelerate, and by the age of 12, the bones no longer differ from those of an adult. In this stage, sports that require agility, flexibility, reaction time, attention, and psychological endurance, such

as judo, soccer, table tennis, and badminton, can be recommended as suitable sports for children. These sports help develop physical and mental skills essential for further growth and development. Since there is a difference in the physical and sexual growth of girls and boys at the age of 13-14 [8]. This difference should be taken into account in the process of involving them in various sports. Regardless of the sport chosen, it is advisable for children aged 10-12 to also engage in swimming, athletics, basketball, and gymnastics to ensure proper physical development, normal growth, and posture formation. The age of 13-14, it is not recommended for children to start sports that require special strength and endurance, as the bone development is not yet complete. Sports that place significant strain on the body may negatively affect the growth and overall development of the child's body. At the age of 13-14, it is appropriate to gradually introduce strength-developing movements. During this period, exercises that require endurance, various weight-bearing movements, body-weight exercises, and gymnastics movements using equipment (such as pull-ups, parallel bars, and jumps on various apparatus) can be taught. Children at this age can regularly engage in sports like athletics, judo, football, freestyle wrestling, Greco-Roman wrestling, combat sports, weightlifting, and others. After the age of 15 [9]. The choice of sport can be tailored based on the child's weight, anthropometric measurements, physiological development, psychological condition, and enthusiasm. At this stage, a more precise and consistent sport regimen can be established based on these factors

References

1. Ibragimov, F., & Guseinzade, R. (2013). *Pedagogika*. Baku. (in Russian).
2. Gasymova, L., & Makhmudova, R. (2003). *Pedagogika*. Baku. (in Russian).
3. Zeinalov, N. R., & Akhundov, A. D. (2014). *Detskaya anatomiya, fiziologiya i gigiena*. Baku, (in Russian).
4. Akhmedov, B. A., & Svetlichnaya, N. K. (2024). Formirovanie inklyuzivnoi kompetentsii pedagogov v sfere fizicheskoi kul'tury i sporta. *Research Focus*, 3(5), 147-153. (in Russian).
5. Kharabugi, G. D. (1969). *Teoriya i metodika fizicheskogo vospitaniya*. Moscow. (in Russian).
6. Kuliev, B. S. O. (2014). Prioritety razvitiya fizicheskogo vospitaniya v azerbaidzhanskikh shkolakh. *Gumanitarnye, sotsial'no-ekonomicheskie i obshchestvennye nauki*, (7), 127-130. (in Russian).
7. Agaev, G. G., & Guseinov, S. S. (1989). *Azerbaidzhanskije detskie podvizhnye igry*. Baku.
8. Narimanov, B. A., Alieva, S. A., & Smolevski, V. M. (1988). *Gimnastika*. Baku. (in Russian).
9. Abasov, T. T. (1987). *Sportivnye i podvizhnye igry*. Baku. (in Russian).